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Interview of Phyllis MA, artist, photographer, and editor

About her editorial work

Your work is mainly focused on food, culinary art, and especially mushrooms. Why the field of publishing in addition to photographic work ? And why a zine rather than a book on your mushroom photographs (Mushrooms and friends) ?

As an emerging artist, publishing is an effective and practical way to showcase my photography. The format of a publication allows slow exploration of a visual topic in a series. I really enjoy making work this way because it counteracts the oversaturation of images in today's culture, especially on social media.

Mushrooms and Friends is my zine series focused on fungal still lifes. So far, there have been 3 issues released – roughly one issue per year, although there is no set schedule. Each zine shows an accumulation of mushrooms that I encountered, along with short writing and identifications of the mushrooms. The zine format made more sense for the project as it could be quickly designed, produced and released. Also, it allowed me to be more experimental in the themes and graphic design. I would love to have a *Mushrooms and Friends* book published one day but it will likely take me years to produce.

Concerning mushrooms, does the symbolism of these influence you in your productions ? Did the fact that they are associated with mold (and therefore death) play a role in the way you stage them ?

My photos feature mushrooms in imaginary and surreal arrangements – certainly inspired by mushrooms' associations with decay, magic, transformation and otherworldliness. Some mushrooms are staged as if growing from food like a slice of orange or a head of cabbage. While these are not scientific portrayals, the images reference fungi's role in decay and death. However, death here is not a gloomy ending, but rather an important step that ushers in new life. Without fungi breaking down organic matter in a forest, new organisms cannot flourish and the forest would cease to exist.

What are your sources of inspiration for Mushrooms and Friends (painting, photography, literature, science, etc.) ?

I have a collection of vintage mushroom and ikebana (Japanese floral arrangement) books that I frequently look to for inspiration. Some influential books I've read are *Entangled Life* by Merlin Sheldrake, *The Mushroom at the End of the World* by Anna Lowenhaupt Tsing, and *How to Do Nothing* by Jenny Odell.

Do you see an evolution in the aesthetics, the formal characteristics you choose ?

Stylistically, the series has maintained aesthetics of minimal still lifes with bright colors.

Each issue showcases different varieties of mushrooms that have more and more unusual features and background stories.

Is publishing regular ? Do you have a maximum price to set for your editions, and if so, why ? How do you decide the number of copies for each edition ?

The publishing is not regular simply because I don't encounter mushrooms on a regular schedule, and I think imposing a deadline would negatively affect my creativity. With each issue, I try to push my work in new directions so I don't bore myself.

For *Mushrooms and Friends*, the price per copy is set at \$25 (USD), which is roughly 5 times the production price. This is a common practice to account for consignments, because typically when you sell your publication at a bookstore, the store will keep around 50% of the retail price.

The zines are printed as an open edition, and the number of copies produced is roughly calculated based on how the previous issue sold.

Are you yourself a buyer and collector of artists' editions ? And if so, do you think that your collection influences, even unconsciously, your plastic work ? Or are you influenced by another type of collection ?

Yes, I enjoy buying and collecting artists' books. My collection serves as an important source of inspiration and a library for reference. Beyond the content of the books, I think it's really fun to observe the tactile nature of books – the feel of the papers, the bindings, and even the smells.